

Coherent wavefield reconstruction improves event location with dense seismic arrays

Lei Li^{1,2,3*} and Benjamin Schwarz⁴

1. Key Laboratory of Metallogenic Prediction of Nonferrous Metals and Geological Environment Monitoring (Central South University), Ministry of Education, 410083 Changsha, China.
2. Hunan Key Laboratory of Nonferrous Resources and Geological Hazard Exploration, 410083 Changsha, China.
3. School of Geosciences and Info-Physics, Central South University, 410083 Changsha, China.
4. Fraunhofer Institute for Wind Energy Systems IWES, 28359 Bremen, German.

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Other Supplementary Material for this manuscript includes the following:

Movies S1 to S5

Introduction

The text, figures and table included in this document are designed to complement and support the analysis presented in the main text.

Text S1: Generation of realistic waveform data

To generate realistic synthetic data, we use the same model parameters of event ML203 and event 24021, including the velocity model, source parameters, and station geometry, to simulate the vertical-component waveforms, and then add corresponding field noise from each station to respective traces of synthetic waveforms. The noise is created and defined by the following equation [1] :

$$Noise = \frac{A_{noise}}{mean(|A_{noise}|)} \cdot mean(|A_{synthetic}|) \cdot NL, \quad (S1)$$

where A_{noise} is the noise retrieved from field waveforms on each trace at a given time window before the first arrival, $A_{synthetic}$ is the computed amplitudes for the

given model parameters, NL means the level or intensity of the noise, which approximates the reversed value of the SNR. The selected noise amplitudes are extended recurrently to match the noise-free synthetic amplitudes. In this work, we select the first 400 samples of noise amplitudes from each trace to resemble the field noise and set the noise level as 0, 5, and 10, denoting them as noise-free, SNR~1, and SNR<1, respectively. The *Noise* is then added to the original synthetic amplitudes to obtain realistic waveforms with field noise:

$$A_{real} = A_{synthetic} + Noise . \quad (S2)$$

The noisy synthetic waveforms are normalized trace by trace before entering the reconstruction and location workflow.

Text S2: Discussion

While the noise suppression and regularization capabilities of coherent wavefield reconstruction could be successfully demonstrated for the LASSO array, it needs to be stated that not all array configurations are equally suitable for such a reconstruction. Especially very directional array configurations, such as the typically T-shaped array geometries introduced for nuclear test monitoring make a 3D spatio-temporal reconstruction of the wavefield more challenging in practice. However, if only coherent data enhancement is concerned, 2D projections of wavefields can still be successfully regularized and enhanced with reduced (2D) moveout operators and directional (2D) apertures. One prominent use case of such 2D projections is fiber-optic distributed acoustic sensing (DAS), where strain or strain rate is recorded along the local axis of buried fiber-optic cables [2],[3]. In the context of volcano monitoring, coherent data enhancement techniques were demonstrated to improve the sensitivity and overall data quality of DAS arrays [4]. No matter whether 2D or 3D applications are concerned, the appropriate choice of local spatial aperture dimensions are crucial for the success of the method. There exists a natural trade-off between fold (the more neighboring traces are included the better are the noise suppression capabilities) and wavefield complexity (the smaller the aperture, the more wavefield complexity can be honored). So, while a simple circular aperture radius of 5 km led to reasonable results for LASSO, more complicated and possibly spatially varying aperture dimensions should be utilized under less favorable conditions (compare supplementary Figures S2 and S3).

We present the imaging results for all considered events to further demonstrate the effectiveness of waveform reconstruction, but the source-receiver geometry is not the only dominant factor for stacking-based methods, other factors like velocity model and stacking operators also directly affect the final imaging results. Besides, this work only presents a qualitative evaluation of the imaging resolution. A detailed quantitative analysis of the imaging resolution is out of the scope of the current study, and we are aware that a comprehensive uncertainty evaluation of source imaging remains challenging so far. Though we only investigate the performance of coherent wavefield reconstruction with stacking-based seismic location, we believe the proposed method can introduce

benefits for other array-based techniques and other scenarios associated with dense seismic arrays. For example, time reverse techniques rely on dense and regular wavefields to produce coherent and focused imaging results [5]. We believe reconstructed wavefields have good potential to achieve improved subsurface structures and source characterizations by enhancing the imaging profiles. Besides, the enhanced and regularized wavefields can be used for various subsequent seismic processing, such as constraining velocity tomography and seismic migration, detecting small earthquakes, and facilitating source mechanism inversion.

References

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Figure S1. The flowchart of the proposed wavefield reconstruction method.

Figure S2. Number of traces in different apertures

Figure S3. Coherence of the four field events using different apertures

Figure S4. Reconstructed wavefields of the four field events using different apertures

Figure S5. Unreconstructed and reconstructed waveforms of the four field events. (a) event ML008, (b) event 24021, (c) event ML203, (d) event 23183. The left column corresponds to raw traces of unreconstructed waveforms, and the right column are those of reconstructed waveforms. Only portions (50 traces) of the seismograms are shown.

Figure S6. STA/LTA traces of the unreconstructed raw waveforms and reconstructed waveforms of the synthetic and field event ML203. The left column corresponds to STA/LTA traces of unreconstructed waveforms, and the right column are those of reconstructed waveforms. (a) to (c) correspond to different noise levels, (d) corresponds to the field event ML203. Only portions (about 50 traces) of the seismograms are shown.

Figure S7. The source imaging results for the four field events using raw traces. (a) event ML008, (b) event 24021, (c) event ML203, (d) event 23183. The left column corresponds to the result of unreconstructed waveforms, and the right column images result from reconstructed waveforms. Reference locations from the catalog and/or previous studies are indicated as white circles. Please note the degradation of the depth resolution of event 24021 and event 23183, mainly caused by the array geometry and the properties of the chosen stacking operator. The horizontal resolution of the images, on the other hand, remains consistently high.

Figure S8. The source imaging results for the four field events using STA/LTA traces. (a) event ML008, (b) event 24021, (c) event ML203, (d) event 23183. The left column corresponds to the result of unreconstructed waveforms, and the right column images result from reconstructed waveforms. Reference locations from the catalog and/or previous studies are indicated by a circle.

Movies S1 to S5: Synchronized animations of the raw data (left), its reconstruction (center) and the estimated waveform coherence (right) for the four field events and the synthetic event ML203 (SNR<1).